

Sophytes' Helmet.

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In numismatic discourse,¹ much has been made of the resemblance of the Sophytes helmeted male head found on the obverse of the coinage of Sopyhtes (*Andragoras and Sophytes Series 8*)² to that found on Susa trophy series of Seleukos I (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Helmeted male head depictions: (a) Sophytes and (b) Seleukos I, Susa.³

The similarity of style and presentation has been the basis of the chronological interpretation that these coinages are close contemporaries, with the former assimilating the imagery of the latter. However, a comparison of the two obverse images, each of a helmeted male head, reveals some notable differences of detail that argue against the copying or assimilation of the Susa helmeted head into that of the Sophytes issue. Both coin types depict a helmeted male head in profile on the obverse. Beyond the fact that in each case the imagery consists of a helmeted male head there are only two general components of shared detail in the imagery, the presence of a cheek guard on the helmet, accompanied by a decorative visor with a volute termination. Aside from the obvious differences in the adornment of the helmet and cheek guard, five very significant differences of detail and style are apparent. Firstly, the helmet on Sophytes head bears a prominent metal crest decorated with a series of volute links on the side of the crest. In contrast, the helmet bowl on the Susa head is smooth, devoid of a crest of any sort. Secondly, the helmet on the Sophytes issues exposes a realistically depicted ear of the male head, whereas as that of the male head on the Susa type is not visible, fully covered by a prominently developed facial guard. Thirdly, the cheek guard depicted on the Sophytes helmet is clearly attached to the bowl of the helmet via a linear hinge along the base of the helmet bowl, protruding from beneath the inner end of the helmet's visor, whereas there is no apparent mechanism of fixture of the cheek guard to the helmet bowl on the Susa depiction. It simply

¹ Cunningham (1866): 222; Gardner (1886): xix-xx; Bopearachchi (1996): 25-26; Kritt (2017): 64-74. Refer to Footnote 9 for Head's (1906) and Whitehead's dissenting views, supported by the analysis of Taylor (2019).

² Taylor (2019): 59-61.

³ Both coins are tetradrachms: (a) Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 365 and (b) Triton XXIII, lot 460.

merges with the helmet bowl beneath the visor, a fixed component of a single piece helmet. Fourthly, the neck guard of the helmet in each case is of a different design. That of the Sophytes helmet closely conforms to the nape of the neck, looping down behind the exposed ear of the head. On the Susa depiction the neck guard is more rigidly vertical, and fails to conform to the nape of the neck. Finally, the depiction of the base of the neck is markedly different on the two types. That of the Sophytes emission is defined by a sharp neck truncation on which a mint mark (MNA or M) can be discerned on two (types 8.1 and 8.2) of the three issues. In contrast, the base of the neck on the Susa type is concealed by a leopard skin, tied at the front of the neck by the paws. These differences of detail far exceed the similarities. They indicate that both images evolved separately from each other, rather than being the result of copying or assimilation of one by the other.

Andragoras and Sophytes
Series 1.1

Helmet detail is true to the early 3rd Century BC Athenian prototype.

Andragoras and Sophytes
Series 2.15

Introduction of the volute end termination of the inner end of the decorative visor.

Andragoras and Sophytes
Series 7.1

Introduction of the metallic helmet crest decorated with linked volutes, replacing the cropped "horse hair" depiction of the Athenian imitative owls. Neck guard more closely conforms to neck.

Andragoras and Sophytes
Series 8.2

Cheek guards added to the helmet. The Attic decorative elements are dropped replaced by an inscribed laurel wreath design. Neck guard further modified to conform to outline of the neck and ear.

Figure 2. Evolution of helmet depiction from an artistic construct (Series 1) to the realistic depiction on the Sophytes emission (Series 8).⁴

⁴ All coins are tetradrachms, top to bottom: Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 344; Roma Numismatics E-Sale 44, lot 312; Roma Numismatics XIV, lot 364; Roma Numismatics XV, lot 340.

An examination of the preceding issues in the coinage that culminated in the emission of the Sophytes helmeted head argues mores strongly for evolution of the depiction of the Sophytes type helmet from the Attic style helmet worn by Athena on the imitative owls of Series 1 and 2. This evolution is characterised by the progressive replacement of purely artistic devices on the helmet by details reflecting the features of true to life helmets (Figure 2). As I have noted in a previous publication:

In the progression of iconographic detail from the Athena head of Series 2 to that of the androgynous Athena of Series 7 and then to the male head of Series 8 we see a series of details develop that argue more strongly for convergent evolution of the helmeted male head design, rather than a direct assimilation of the Susa types. The laurel wreath decoration of the helmet bowl, plus the bird wing adornment of the cheek guard, the latter thematically carrying through into the design an iconographic element associated with the dominant ‘birds of a feather’ iconography of the reverse of the coinage, argue strongly for a degree of convergent evolution of the helmeted head design, rather than assimilation. The helmet depicted on the coinage of Sophytes probably reflected reality. Supporting this idea, is a remarkable sculpted helmeted male head, dating to the second century BC, recovered in the excavations of the Parthian royal palace at Nisa, in eastern Parthia [Figure 3]. Although it bears a fulmen on the cheek guards, the helmet is of near identical form to that depicted on the Sophytes coins, including the detail of the metal crest. The sculpted head is inferred to be that of a Parthian soldier wearing a Hellenistic style helmet; the style of helmet influenced by the former enemy from whom control of Parthia was wrested.⁵

Figure 3. Helmeted head of second century BC Parthian warrior from Nisa.⁶

⁵ Taylor (2019): 59-61.

⁶ Image source [Parthian warrior head](#). Also refer to [Excavations of Staraiia Nisa](#).

Further support for the theory that the helmet on the Sophytes issues is a realistic depiction of a military helmet of the mid-3rd century BC is found in the closely styled 3rd century BC helmet found in a warrior's burial at Kerch in the Crimea.⁷ This helmet made of iron, overlaid with silver, is believed to have originated from Milos in the southwestern Cyclades in the first half of the 3rd century BC. Although only a small portion of the neck guard is preserved, the helmet is of the same overall form and outline as the Sophytes helmet. It bears an identical metal crest, volute terminated visor design and cheek guards separated from the remnant neck guard sufficiently to expose the ear of the wearer. On the left side of the helmet is preserved the outline of the linear hinge edge to which was affixed the cheek guard in an identical fashion to that depicted on the Sophytes coinage. So close is the form and style of this helmet, it could suffice as a model for the style of helmet depicted on the coinage of Sophytes.

Conclusion

The hypothesis that the helmeted head on the Sophytes issue assimilated that of the Seleukos I Susa trophy coinage is a misleading fallacy. The differences observed between the two depictions far outweigh the minor general points similarity, to the extent that the argument that the former copies and assimilates the latter has no foundation. In the coinage of Andragoras and Sophytes we witness a progression in helmet depiction from the purely artistic construct of the Attic helmet depicted on the initial imitative Athenian coinage (Series 1) to an evolved realistic helmet depiction on the coinage of Sophytes (Series 7 & 8), one that clearly dates to the 3rd century BC.⁸ With this insight, the inferred chronological linkage between the Susa trophy issues of Seleukos I and the eastern coinage in the name of Sophytes collapses. As a consequence, the dating to the late 4th century BC of the preceding succession of mint control linked imitative owl and eagle issues⁹ (*Andragoras and Sophytes* Series 1-5) as proposed by previous scholars¹⁰ is unsustainable. Rather, a mid-3rd century BC date is the only viable option. This downdated chronology is supported comprehensive numismatic analysis of the coinage,¹¹ details of the iconographic development on the imitative owls of Series 2,¹² plus the sparsely documented hoard evidence.¹³

Acknowledgements

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⁷ Now in the State Hermitage Museum of St. Petersburg (Inv. No. II.1834-42). [Web link to Inv. No. II.1834-42](#). Illustrated in Alexinsky D. "Between Hellas and the Barbarians" in *Alexander the Great 2000 Years of Treasures*. The Australian Museum 2012: 106-123, no. 31.

⁸ Head (1906): 14 similarly noted that "*the helmet of Sophytes on the obverse bears a very remarkable resemblance to the helmet of Athena on the drachms of the same Indian weight*" while Whitehead (1943): 60 noted that "*The [Sophytes] drachm is not a direct imitation of any existing piece; the designs are original...*" The astute observations of Head and Whitehead were largely ignored by subsequent scholars in favour of the superficial similarity to the Susa trophy issues of Seleukos I.

⁹ Bopearachchi (1996): 25-27.

¹⁰ Whitehead (1943); Nicolett-Pierre and Amandry (1990); Bopearachchi (1996) and (1998).

¹¹ Taylor (2019) and (2020(a)).

¹² Taylor (2020(a)) and (2020(b)).

¹³ Taylor (2019): 75-78 and Taylor (2020(c)): 2-3.

Bibliography

- Alexinsky D. 2012. Between Hellas and the Barbarians in *Alexander the Great 2000 Years of Treasures*. The Australian Museum (2012): 106-123, catalogue no. 31.
- Bopearachchi, O. 1996. Sophytes, the Enigmatic Ruler of Central Asia." *Nomismatika Khronika* 15 (1996): 19-32.
- Bopearachchi, O. 1998. *Sylloge Numomorum Graecorum: The Collection of the American Numismatic Society*. Part 9. *Graeco-Bactrian and Indo-Greek Coins*. New York: The American Numismatic Society.
- Cunningham, A. 1866. Coin of the Indian Prince Sophytes: A Contemporary of Alexander the Great. *Numismatic Chronicle* New Series 6: 220-231.
- Gardner, P. 1886. *The Coins of the Greek and Scythic Kings of Bactria and India*. London: British Museum.
- Head, B. V. 1906. The Earliest Graeco-Bactrian and Graeco-Indian Coins. *Numismatic Chronicle* Fourth Series, 6: 1-16.
- Houghton, A. and Lorber, C. 2002. *Seleucid Coins a Comprehensive Catalogue. Part 1 Seleucus I to Antiochus III*. The American Numismatic Society in association with Classical Numismatic Group.
- Kritt, B. 2017. *The Seleucid mint of Ai Khanoum*. Classical Numismatic Studies 9. Classical Numismatic Group, Lancaster, Pennsylvania.
- Nicolet-Pierre, H. and M. Amandry. 1994. Un nouveau trésor de monnaies d'argent pseudo-athéniennes venu d'Afghanistan (1990). *Revue Numismatique* 36: 34-54
- Taylor, L. W. H. 2019. Birds of a Feather, Brothers in Arms: The Coinage of Andragoras and Sophytes. *American Journal of Numismatics* 31: 21-79.
- Taylor, L. W. H. 2020(a). The *Kerykeion* mint control linked coinage of Andragoras and Sophytes. *Koinon* III (in press).
- Taylor, L. W. H. 2020(b). A Commentary on the Significance of the Development of the Decorative Visor Design on the Series 2 Imitative Owls of Andragoras. A working paper (Version v. 1.0) *Zenodo*: [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3961283](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3961283)
- Taylor, L. W. H. 2020(c). A Pseudo-Seleukid Imitative Owl. A working paper (Version v. 1.0) *Zenodo*: [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3966748](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3966748)
- Whitehead, R. B. 1943. The Eastern Satrap Sophytes. *Numismatic Chronicle* Sixth Series, 3: 60-72.